

Comparative Analysis of LULCC Climate Studies and Ground Water Quality Between Coimbatore North and South Zones of Tamilnadu

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Abstract India is one of the developing countries in the world with highest population than any other countries. Coimbatore is the third largest cities and one of the industrialized cities in Tamil Nadu. It is also called as Textile Capital and Manchester of South India. The city is located in the banks of Noyyal River. This research paper mainly aims to analyse the comparison of Land Use and Land Cover Changes, Climatic variations and Ground Water level in the South and North zones of Coimbatore. The various sources of data are acquired for last 4 years - 2019, 2020, 2021 & 2022 for detecting the changes in Land Use/Cover and fluctuations in the climate and ground water level. This analysis helps to find the changes and impact of urban development and the key factors which affects the climate in the particular zones based on the Land Use and Land Cover (LULC). For the comparative analysis, the Remote sensing and Geospatial data are used with extraction spatial analysis tool in order to examine the changes. The data reveals concerning trends in Coimbatore's environment: a 2.26% increase in built-up areas accompanied by a 6% decrease in agricultural land, indicative of rapid urbanization. Temperature dropped by 1.29°C, possibly influenced by urbanization, while rainfall consistently decreased, particularly in urbanizing areas. Fluctuations in groundwater levels highlight potential stress on water resources due to changing land use patterns. Urgent action is warranted, emphasizing sustainable land management, urban planning, and conservation efforts to mitigate environmental impacts and ensure long-term resilience for the region. This makes the drastic impact in the greenhouse gas emission.

Keywords Land Use and Land Cover Changes (LULCC), Climate Studies, Ground Water level, Coimbatore South and North zones, Greenhouse Gas Emissions.

Introduction

Coimbatore, (Latitude: 11°00'19" N, Longitude: 76°57'58" E) situated in the western expanse of Tamil Nadu, India, epitomizes a captivating blend of tradition and progress, weaving a narrative of diverse landscapes, economic prowess, educational excellence, cultural vibrancy, and modern infrastructure. Nestled between the majestic Western Ghats and the neighbouring state of Kerala, the district's topography encompasses rolling plains, dense forests, and the scenic contours of the Western Ghats, contributing to its natural splendor. As the bustling district headquarters, Coimbatore has earned the sobriquet "Manchester of South India," owing to its prominence in the textile industry. However, its economic canvas extends far beyond textiles, encompassing thriving sectors such as engineering, information technology, and agriculture, fostering a spirit of entrepreneurship that resonates throughout the city. Industrial zones, teeming with small and medium-scale enterprises, bear witness to the city's industrial prowess, with engineering firms gaining global recognition for their products. Coimbatore stands as a hub for education, hosting renowned universities, engineering colleges, and research institutions, attracting a diverse student population from across the country. This academic dynamism contributes to the city's intellectual capital. Cultural vibrancy permeates every facet of Coimbatore, with festivals celebrated with fervor, traditional arts flourishing, and cultural events shaping the city's social fabric. Land use and land cover are integral components in the assessment and management of Earth's surface characteristics. Land use refers to the diverse array of human activities that shape and modify the land for specific purposes. These activities encompass residential, commercial, industrial, agricultural, recreational, and institutional functions, among others. Essentially, land use captures the anthropogenic imprint on the landscape, reflecting the ways in which societies utilize and interact with their environment. On the other hand, land cover pertains to the physical and biological attributes covering the land surface. This encompasses natural elements like forests, water bodies, and grasslands, as well as human-made features such as urban areas and transportation infrastructure. While land use and land cover are distinct concepts, they are intricately connected. Human activities, denoted by land use, often result in alterations to the physical characteristics of the land, manifesting as changes in land cover. The conversion of natural landscapes to urban areas or agricultural fields exemplifies this dynamic relationship. Monitoring and analyzing land use and land cover changes are critical for environmental assessment, resource management, and sustainable development planning. Technologies like remote sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) play pivotal roles in collecting and analyzing data, providing valuable insights into the evolving nature of the Earth's surface and guiding informed decision-making for responsible land management.

Objectives

The primary focus of this study is to investigate the urban development dynamics and associated environmental impacts, specifically concerning temperature variations and fluctuations in groundwater levels within Coimbatore district. Leveraging satellite data analysis from diverse sources, the research aims to discern patterns and trends to address pollution concerns, notably greenhouse gas emissions and temperature alterations. By meticulously comparing data from various years, the study endeavors to discern the evolution of urbanization and its effects on the local environment. The

overarching goal is to provide meaningful insights and potential solutions to mitigate the adverse consequences of urban development, particularly in terms of pollution and climatic changes. Through rigorous analysis and interpretation of satellite-derived information, this research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between urban growth and environmental sustainability, facilitating informed decision-making for the region's future development and well-being.

Fig. 1 Study Area – Coimbatore District

Methodology

Data Analysis of Land Use and Land Cover Change

The source data of Land Use and Land Cover Changes are taken from the Sentinel-2 ESRI land cover data. The particular area of India according to the study area has been taken and the layer has been added into ArcGIS software.

Fig. 2 Source Data of LULCC from Sentinel 2 ESRI Land Cover

Fig. 3 Source Data of LULCC of Coimbatore District from Sentinel 2 ESRI Land Cover

The detection of Land use and Land cover changes are done using ArcGIS Software for the year between 2019 and 2022. There is a difference in the urban area and agricultural regions over the years. Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc. (ESRI) - multi-spectral data spanning 13 bands in the visible, near infrared, and short-wave infrared, with spatial resolution ranging from 10 meters to 60 meters. Sentinel-2 is continually collecting imagery from two Earth observation satellites that provide imagery for any land-based location in the world every 5-7 days.

Fig. 4 Graph of LULC Changes from 2019-2022 (Area in Miles)

Fig. 5 Land Use and Land Cover Changes at 2019

Fig. 6 Land Use and Land Cover Changes at 2020

Fig. 7 Land Use and Land Cover Changes at 2021

Fig. 8 Land Use and Land Cover Changes at 2022

Table 1 Data Difference Analysis

Legends	2019	Area Change %	2020	Area Change %
Water	488176	0.6588633	581396	0.784677
Trees	19793119	26.7136437	23131186	31.21884
Flooded Vegetation	783	0.00105677	1924	0.002597
Agriculture	32108657	43.3352228	29537176	39.86464
Built-up Area	12394993	16.728815	12951894	17.48043
Bare ground	11439	0.01543857	10816	0.014598
Wetland	9296442	12.5468775	7878777	10.63354
TOTAL AREA	74093670		74093670	

Legends	2021	Area Change %	2022	Area Change %	Area Difference between 2019-2022
Water	647529	0.873933	726735	0.980833	-0.32 %
Trees	24145138	32.58732	26204789	35.36711	-8.65 %
Flooded Vegetation	1381	0.001864	3211	0.004334	-0.0033 %
Agriculture	29546293	39.87695	27661322	37.33291	6 %
Built-up Area	13791429	18.61351	14066316	18.9845	-2.26 %
Bare ground	7968	0.010754	4637	0.006258	0.009 %
Wetland	5953350	8.034897	5426168	7.323389	5.22 %
TOTAL AREA	74093670		74093670		

Area Values in miles

NEGATIVE IMPACT

POSITIVE IMPACT

The analysis of land use and land cover changes in Coimbatore over the past four years reveals significant shifts, particularly in the built-up area and agricultural lands. The data indicates a concerning trend characterized by an increase in built-up areas by 2.26% and a corresponding decrease in agricultural lands by 6%. These changes signify a substantial transformation in the landscape, with implications for various aspects of the environment and socio-economic dynamics. The expansion of built-up areas suggests rapid urbanization or infrastructural development within the district. While urbanization can bring economic growth and opportunities, it often comes at the expense of natural ecosystems and agricultural land. The encroachment upon agricultural lands poses a threat to food security and rural livelihoods, as well as the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services provided by agricultural landscapes. Moreover, the observed changes in land use may have several other consequences, both positive and negative. On the positive side, urbanization may lead

to improved access to amenities, better infrastructure, and increased employment opportunities. However, these benefits may be overshadowed by negative impacts such as environmental degradation, loss of green spaces, increased pollution, and strain on resources like water and energy. Furthermore, the disproportionate ratio between positive and negative impacts highlights the severity of the situation. While some benefits may accrue from urban expansion, the overall balance appears to tilt towards adverse outcomes, particularly concerning the loss of agricultural land. This underscores the need for careful planning and sustainable land management practices to mitigate the negative effects of urbanization and preserve vital agricultural resources. Addressing the threat posed by the increase in built-up areas and the decline in agricultural lands in Coimbatore requires a multi-faceted approach. This approach could include implementing land-use planning policies that prioritize conservation and sustainable development, promoting agricultural practices that enhance productivity and resilience, and fostering community engagement and awareness regarding the importance of preserving agricultural land and natural ecosystems. The observed changes in land use and land cover in Coimbatore reflect a complex interplay of socio-economic factors and environmental dynamics. While urbanization may offer opportunities for development, it is essential to balance growth with the preservation of agricultural land and environmental integrity to ensure the long-term well-being of the region and its inhabitants.

Temperature Analysis

Table 2 Temperature Data (°C)

The temperature data are the standard data from one of the satellites for the visualization of the fluctuating changes for the recent years.

YEAR	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC	ANN
2019	24.4	28.9	31.28	32.08	31.6	29.09	27.91	26.75	26.39	25.65	24.99	23.94	27.73°C
2020	25.05	27.15	30.59	31.67	31.7	28.21	26.63	26.72	25.98	25.93	24.87	23.14	27.3°C
2021	23.42	24.5	28.13	30.19	28.55	27.59	26.69	26.82	26.35	25.72	24.27	22.91	26.26°C
2022	24.05	25.62	28.92	29.99	28.62	27.27	26.69	26.13	26.26	25.67	24.05	23.98	26.44°C

SOURCE:

NASA/POWER CERES/MERRA2 Native Resolution Monthly and Annual

Dates (month/day/year): 01/01/2019 through 12/31/2022

Location: **Latitude 11.1239 Longitude 77.3656** (Around Vadavalli)

Elevation from MERRA-2: Average for 0.5 x 0.625-degree lat/lon region = 284.14-meter

Parameter(s): **T2M MERRA-2 Temperature at 2 Meters (C)**

Fig. 9 Graph showing Temperature variation from 2019-2022

Nasa/Power Ceres/Merra2 Native Resolution Spatial Temporal Resolution

The resolution is 1.0° latitude by 1.0° longitude for the radiation data sets and ½° latitude by ⅝° longitude for the

meteorological data sets. The data from NASA's power data reveals fluctuating changes in average temperatures from 2019 to 2022. Over this period, there's a noticeable trend of decreasing temperatures, with the average temperature dropping from 27.73°C in 2019 to 26.44°C in 2022, representing a decrease of 1.29%. One significant factor contributing to these temperature fluctuations is urbanization. As urban areas expand, they tend to absorb more heat, a phenomenon known as the urban heat island effect. The proliferation of concrete surfaces, buildings, and infrastructure in urban environments leads to increased absorption and retention of solar radiation, causing temperatures to rise. This effect is particularly pronounced in densely populated cities like Coimbatore, where rapid urbanization is occurring.

Rainfall Data Analysis

The precipitation data has been acquired from India- Water Resource Information System (WRIS) for the visualization of the fluctuations of the Rainfall between 2019 and 2022.

Table 3 Monthly Rainfall data for the year 2019

Monthly rainfall (in mm) trends for Coimbatore from 01-Jan-2019 to 31-Dec-2019		
Dates	NORMAL (mm)	ACTUAL (mm)
Jan-19	0	0.56
Feb-19	0	2.71
Mar-19	0	2.27
Apr-19	0	19.09
May-19	0	33.52
Jun-19	38.2	58.48
Jul-19	56.7	48.87
Aug-19	41.8	448.43
Sep-19	56.2	186.4
Oct-19	153.2	271.76
Nov-19	123.4	107.37
Dec-19	50.4	50.7

Fig. 10 Rainfall Data (Max) - 2019

Fig. 11 Rainfall Data as Graph – 2019

Table 4 Monthly Rainfall data for the year 2020

Monthly rainfall (in mm) trends for Coimbatore from 01-Jan-2020 to 31-Dec-2020		
Dates	NORMAL (mm)	ACTUAL (mm)
Jan-20	0	0.96
Feb-20	0	0.01
Mar-20	0	17.95
Apr-20	0	76.46
May-20	0	56.36
Jun-20	38.2	148.17
Jul-20	56.7	115.04
Aug-20	41.8	287.61
Sep-20	56.2	272.33
Oct-20	153.2	81.35
Nov-20	123.4	183.42
Dec-20	50.4	67.77
Max. Rainfall	153.2	287.6

From fig. 10, fig. 12, fig 14 seen that the rainfall from the WRIS data. The amount of rainfall has been decreased from 2019 – 2022. The amount of rainfall varies at different locations of different latitude and longitude. The above explained data are at one location **Latitude & Longitude – (11.18149 N | 76.99439 E)**. Likewise, the values changes but for the analysis the image has been observed clearly for the interpretation of rainfall data at North and South regions. (Source: <https://indiawriss.gov.in/wris/#/rainfall>)

and fig. 16, it can be clearly fluctuations has been obtained

Fig. 12 Rainfall Data (Max) – 2020

Fig. 13 Rainfall Data as Graph – 2020

The rainfall data obtained from the WRIS shows the clear view of fluctuating changes in the regions where the urban development occurs. The Fig. 5 to 8 where the land use and land cover changes represented and the Fig. 18 – 22 where the rainfall data represented, the fluctuations in the climate has been visualized and compared. It is typically shown that the fluctuations in the climate occurs due to the development of urban in the Middle and North side of the city whereas the southern part of the city remains constant and shows only slight variations in the climate. Groundwater depth data was collected from various monitoring points across Coimbatore city. The data included measurements taken over a specific time period, allowing for the assessment of fluctuations. Zones were delineated based on urban and non-urban areas. Urban areas were identified by higher population density and significant anthropogenic activities. Analysis revealed notable fluctuations in groundwater depth across different zones within Coimbatore city. Urban areas exhibited higher depths, with the groundwater level increasing by 30m to 50m compared to non-urban areas. This trend suggests heightened demand and potential stress on groundwater resources in urbanized regions. Conversely, non-urban areas displayed

Table 5 Monthly Rainfall data for the year 2021

Monthly rainfall (in mm) trends for Coimbatore from 01-Jan-2021 to 31-Dec-2021		
Dates	NORMAL (mm)	ACTUAL (mm)
Jan-21	0	111.17
Feb-21	0	20.14
Mar-21	0	7.98
Apr-21	0	58.7
May-21	0	165.83
Jun-21	38.2	152.93
Jul-21	56.7	292.5
Aug-21	41.8	187.32
Sep-21	56.2	165.95
Oct-21	153.2	324.3
Nov-21	123.4	288.54
Dec-21	50.4	62.95
Max. Rainfall	153.2	324.3

Fig. 14 Rainfall Data (Max) - 2021

Fig. 15 Rainfall Data as Graph - 2021

minimal fluctuations in groundwater depth, indicating relatively stable conditions. The observed fluctuations in groundwater depth underscore the impact of urbanization and climatic variations on water resources in Coimbatore city. High groundwater depths in urban areas signify increased extraction rates and potential depletion of aquifers. Sustainable water management strategies are imperative to mitigate adverse effects and ensure the long-term availability of groundwater resources.

Table 6 Monthly Rainfall data for the year 2022

Monthly rainfall (in mm) trends for Coimbatore from 01-Jan-2022 to 31-Dec-2022		
Dates	NORMAL (mm)	ACTUAL (mm)
Jan-22	0	12.23
Feb-22	0	1.06
Mar-22	0	21.78
Apr-22	0	92.77
May-22	0	159.92
Jun-22	38.2	115.43
Jul-22	56.7	421.96
Aug-22	41.8	373.78
Sep-22	56.2	174.36
Oct-22	153.2	182.62
Nov-22	123.4	168.79
Dec-22	50.4	95.53
Max. Rainfall	153.2	422

Fig. 16 Rainfall Data (Max) - 2022

Fig. 17 Rainfall Data as Graph – 2022

Fig. 18 Avg. Rainfall – 2019

Fig. 19 Avg. Rainfall – 2020

Fig.21 Avg. Rainfall – 2021

Fig.22 Avg. Rainfall – 2022

Results and Discussions

Land Use and Land Cover Usages

The analysis of land use and land cover changes in Coimbatore City over the past four years reveals significant shifts, particularly in built-up areas and agricultural lands. There has been a concerning increase in built-up areas by 2.26%, coupled with a corresponding decrease in agricultural lands by 6%. These changes signify a substantial transformation in the landscape, reflecting rapid urbanization or infrastructural development within the district. The encroachment upon agricultural lands poses a threat to food security, rural livelihoods, and biodiversity. The observed changes in land use underscore the need for careful planning and sustainable land management practices to mitigate adverse impacts and preserve vital agricultural resources.

Temperature Trends

Data from NASA's power data indicates fluctuating changes in average temperatures from 2019 to 2022 in Coimbatore City. Over this period, there's a noticeable trend of decreasing temperatures, with the average temperature dropping from 27.73°C in 2019 to 26.44°C in 2022, representing a decrease of 1.29%. Urbanization is identified as a significant factor contributing to these temperature fluctuations, with the urban heat island effect exacerbating the situation. As urban areas expand, they tend to absorb more heat, leading to increased temperatures. This effect is particularly pronounced in densely populated cities like Coimbatore, where rapid urbanization is occurring.

Ground Water Level Analysis

Table 7 Ground Water Level data

Station	Latitude	Longitude	AVG 2019-2022
Ambarampalayam	10.649577	76.91003	1.78 - 4.85
Angalakurichi	10.528625	76.994625	0.16 - 34.6
Annur2	11.233082	77.109399	8.86 - 28.61
Ganesapuram	11.175817	77.055556	17.39 - 31.85
Gopalapuram	10.695823	76.936242	1.25 - 5.9
Kalviramapalayam	11.050285	76.88726	47.02 - 63.4
Kinathukadavu	10.735763	77.029626	2.38 - 7.65
Madukkarai	10.908553	76.966043	6.23 - 17.7
P.N. palayam	11.150135	76.941529	0.85 - 21.3
Pollachi1	10.660709	77.00296	0.45 - 1.46
Ponnaiyur	10.670974	76.933607	2 - 6.55
Saravanampatti	11.061548	76.999525	5.8 - 25.05
Saravanampatti1	11.078799	77.001723	12.2 - 34.08
Sarkar samakulam	11.130546	77.033583	9 - 16.15
Seeliyur	11.183509	76.756737	2.45 - 18.1
Singanallur	10.996131	77.020624	2.65 - 6.65
Sokkanur	10.80476	76.95793	2.55 - 9.82
Sugunapuram1	10.954725	76.943647	13.75 - 32.54
Sulur	11.017699	77.12417	0.8 - 11.1
Vadavalli	11.020572	76.90724	37.6 - 48.4

Ground Water Level
Depth To Water Level(m bgl)

- <2
- 2 - 5
- 5 - 10
- 10 - 20
- 20 - 40
- >40

Rainfall Fluctuations

The analysis of rainfall data obtained from WRIS shows fluctuating changes in rainfall from 2019 to 2022 in Coimbatore City. There has been a decrease in rainfall over this period, particularly in regions undergoing urban development. The fluctuations in rainfall patterns are notably observed in the Middle and North sides of the city, coinciding with areas experiencing significant urban development. Conversely, the southern part of the city shows relatively constant rainfall patterns with only slight variations. These findings suggest a potential correlation between urbanization and changes in local climate patterns, highlighting the need for further investigation and sustainable urban planning strategies to mitigate adverse effects.

Groundwater Table Fluctuations

Groundwater data reveals fluctuations in the average depth of the groundwater table in Coimbatore City. These fluctuations vary across different zones and climatic conditions. The data underscores the dynamic nature of groundwater resources, which are influenced by factors such as rainfall patterns, land use changes, and urban development. Sustainable management of groundwater resources is essential to ensure continued access to clean water for various purposes, including agriculture, industry, and domestic use.

Conclusions

The data analysis conducted reveals concerning trends regarding land use and environmental changes in Coimbatore. The observed increase in built-up areas by 2.26% coupled with a substantial decrease in agricultural lands by 6% signifies rapid urbanization at the expense of natural ecosystems. This shift is likely contributing to fluctuations in temperature, with an average drop of 1.29°C, although mitigated by counterbalancing environmental factors. The consistent decrease in rainfall, particularly in urbanizing regions, suggests potential alterations in local climate patterns. Additionally, varied fluctuations in the groundwater table across different zones indicate stress on water resources, possibly stemming from urban development and altered land use practices. In conclusion, the quantitative analysis underscores the intricate interplay between urbanization, environmental dynamics, and socio-economic factors in Coimbatore. Urgent measures are warranted to promote sustainable land management, meticulous urban planning, and conservation initiatives to

alleviate the adverse impacts on the region's environment. These efforts are essential for fostering long-term resilience and well-being among the populace while safeguarding the integrity of Coimbatore's ecosystems.

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